

**SUCCESSFUL AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF INDRALUPTA
(ALOPECIA AREATA) - A SINGLE CASE STUDY****Dr. Shrikanta*¹, Dr. Ashwini A. Sangolli²**

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ABSTRACT

Indralupta occurs due to excessive consumption of snigdha, ushna, amla, lavana ahara which vitiates vata, pitta leading to avarana of kapha and rakta resulting in hairfall. In the contemporary science, it can be correlated with Alopecia areata, which is an autoimmune disease characterized by patchy hair loss. A holistic approach of ayurveda can be helpful in establishing homeostasis of Dosha and regrowth of hair. Ayurveda has great potential to treat such autoimmune diseases. Here a case of alopecia areata successfully treated with Ayurvedic management.

KEYWORDS: Gandaka rasayana, Triphala guggulu, Ichchbedi rasa, Parijata patra, Nagavalli ointment.

INTRODUCTION

Hair is regarded as an important aspect of beauty and personality in all cultures, and its loss often causes significant emotional and psychological distress. In Ayurvedic literature, hair disorders are described under Kṣudra Roga, among which Indralupta is a common condition characterized by sudden, localized loss of hair on the scalp or beard. Acharya Sushruta has explained that the vitiated Vāta and Pitta doṣas, obstructed by Kapha and Rakta, damage the hair follicles (Romakūpa), leading to hair fall and inhibition of regrowth.^[1] In modern dermatology, Indralupta can be correlated with Alopecia Areata, Alopecia areata (AA) is an

autoimmune disorder that results in the damage of hair follicles leading to hair loss. Hair loss can present in various patterns and with varying severity. Variants include alopecia totalis, which is total scalp hair loss, and alopecia universalis, which is complete body hair loss. Other clinical forms include patchy AA, diffuse AA, AA reticularis, AA ophiasis, AA sisypho, and perinevoid.^[2] The prevalence of this condition is increasing due to stress, nutritional deficiencies, and hormonal imbalance. Contemporary medical management primarily includes corticosteroids and immunosuppressants, which may offer temporary relief but are often associated with side effects and recurrence.

Ayurveda offers a holistic and individualized approach focusing on Doṣa-sāmya, Srotoshodhana, and Romasanjanana (hair follicle regeneration). Classical formulations like Gandaka rasayana, Triphala guggulu, internally and external therapies like Garshana with Parijata patra and lepa with Ichchbedi rasa and nagavalli ointment have been advocated for effective management.

A CASE STUDY

A female patient of age 12 years with chronic history of patchy hair loss on the scalp since 2 years. She had taken the Allopathy treatment for two years and did not find control over the disease. When she approached SSRAMCH, case was clinically diagnosed as Indralupta (Alopecia areata) and advised for Garshana chikitsa and Shamana aushadi. Externally, ichchbedi rasa^[3] grinded along with water and made into paste applied on affected area after proper garshana with parijata patra for five to ten minutes.

The patient was prescribed with internal medicines Gandaka rasayana^[4], triphala guggulu^[5] twice a day along with luke warm water after meal. Patient was asked to visit after every 15 days. On second visit (after 15th day), patient complained of itching and burning after application lepa. Redness in scalp was observed. Patient was prescribed nagavalli lepa^[6] for local application after mild rubbing with parijata patra. On third visit (after a month) improvement was observed on the patches. Preliminary some brownish and some thin hairs appeared in some part of the bald patches [on fourth visit (45th day)], then blackish hair started to grow on fifth visit (60th day). Patches were completely filled up with hair after two months of the treatment. Nagavalli lepa was stopped then and bringaraja taila^[7] started. The hair on the patches gradually grown longer and after two months, they grown as sufficient and similar as that of neighbouring area. Patient was followed every two months then after for period of year. No recurrence was observed during this period.

Table 1: List of internal medication used.

Sl no	Medicine	Dose	Frequency	Anuapana
1	Gandaka rasayana	250mg	Twice a day	Lukewarm water
2	Triphala guggulu	500mg	Twice a day	Lukewarm water
3	Hairrich capsule	500mg	Twice a day	Lukewarm water

Table 2: List of external medications used.

Sl no	Medicine	Method of use
1	Ichhabedi rasa	Made into paste with water and applied on affected area after proper garshana
2	Nagvalli ointment	Applied on affected area after proper garshana
3	Bringaraja taila	Applied on the scalp and gentle massage done once in a day

Table 3: General observations of the patient.

General examinations

Height 132 cm

Blood Pressure 120/80 mmHg

Pulse 68/min

Respiratory rate 19 /min

Temperature Normal

Weight 55 kg

Dashavidha Pariksha

Prakriti- Vata Pittaja

Vikruti Tridosjhaja

Sara- Madhyama

Samhanana- Madhyama

Pramana- madyama

Satva- Avara

Satmya- Avara

Ahara Shakti- Madhyam

Vyayama shakti- madyama

Vaya- bala

Ashtavidha Pariksha

Nadi - vatapittaja

Mala- nirama

Mutra- Samyak

Jihva- samyak

Shabda- prakrut

Sparsha- anushna sheeta

Druk- Prakrita

Akruti- Madyama

SAMPRAPTI

Nidana sevana- Aharaja- ruksha, lavana, ushna pradhana ahara Viharaja- not maintaining the scalp hygiene, non practice of shiroabhyanga or oil application

Vata, pitta prakopa and avarana by kapha and rakta

Hair fall, itching, dryness of the scalp leading to patchy hair loss

Indralupta (alopecia areata)

Before treatment

During treatment

After Treatment

DISCUSSION

Acharya Charaka mentions that Tejas by involving Vatadi Dosha when reaches the scalp, it results in Khalitya (Indralupta).^[8] According to Acharya Sushruta, Pitta along with Vata by involving the roots of hair (Romakoopa) causes fall of hair and thereafter Shleshma along with Shonita obstructs the channel of Romakoopa leading to the stoppage of the regeneration of hair and this condition is known as Indralupta^[9], Khalitya or Ruhya. Thus Vata, Pitta and Kapha Dosha and Rakta Dushya are the main internal causative factors of Indralupta. Charaka in Vimanasthana, while describing the disorders occurring due to over indulgence in Kshara, Lavana and Viruddha Ahara has mentioned the occurrence of Hair Loss as a consequence.^[4] It has been mentioned that the Viruddha Ahara like, simultaneous intake of Lavana (salt) with milk in the diet induces Indralupta, as observed in the people of Saurashtra and Bahlika. Thus, it can be said that a person habituated to excessive Lavana or Kshara intake and taking Viruddha Ahara in routine is prone to have Indralupta. Mithya Ahara and Vihara Manoabhighata like mental stress, fright, anger, shock etc. may collectively increase

the Pitta and Vata Dosha. The Ushna and Tikshna properties of Pitta get augmented whereas the Vata aggravation in terms of Ruksha, Khara and Chala properties. Here an aggravated Pitta (Bhrajaka Pitta) supported by the vitiated Dehoshma burns the Keshabhoomi whereas an increased Vata gives rise to more frequent and comparatively prolonged ShiraSankocha by its Ruksha and Khara Guna. The Snigdhatva and the Pichchhilatva of the normal Kapha Dosha is prevalent throughout the pores of the skin so as to keep it soft and moist. By the augmentation of the Ushna, Tikshna, Ruksha and Khara properties of Pitta and Vata Doshas respectively, the Sneha and the Pichchhilatva of the Kapha Dosha are dried up within the pores of the skin of the scalp thus, obstructing the growth of new hairs, causing Indralupta.

Gandaka rasayana pacifies vitiation of pitta and kapha dosha. It has keshyam ateeva krishnam karoti, in its phalashruthi which indicates its site of action and as a rasayana to scalp and hair. Triphala guggulu is useful to remove the obstruction of kapha to the hair follicle at the level scalp by virtue of its ruksha guna contents of this medicines like guggulu has also have medohara property which again acts on the avarana. Amalaki is also one of the content of triphala guggulu which has keshya and rasayaana action. Triphala guggulu detoxifies body and blood and aids to eliminate toxins accumulated in the body. Triphala Guggulu shows detoxifying and rejuvenating action along with the anti-inflammatory action of guggulu was found to have a marked effect in treatment of alopecia.

In bhaishajyaratnavali, in the treatment of Indralupta it is suggested for scraping of the scalp.^[10] As the patient was bala, mild garshana chikitsa was adopted with parijata patra. After proper garshana for adequate time area was cleaned and paste prepared by rubbing icchabedi tablet with water was applied. Scraping helps in removal of hair root obstruction caused by kapha dosha. When patient was unable to tolerate the icchabedha rasa due to its teekshsa guna, lepa was shifted to nagavalli ointment from SDP pharmacy. Mild garshana was continued along with oral medications and lepa. Once we noticed the hairgrowth on the scalp. That indicates the removal of avarana of kapha. At this we started rasayana, keshya dravyas both externally and internally. Externally we started with bringaraja taila. Internally stopped triphala guggulu and started capsule hairrich.^[11]

CONCLUSION

The patient suffering from Alopecia areata was successfully treated with Ayurvedic Shamana therapy. Nidana parivarjana was also a necessary part of the treatment. This treatment protocol should be clinically evaluated on large number of patients to confirm their efficacy.

REFERENCES

1. Sushruta. Sushruta samhita samhita with the nibandhasangraha commentary of sri dalhanaacharya nidanasthana adhyaya 13/3n2023 edition, choukhamba surbharatin prakashan, Varanasi, 2023; 318.
2. Finner A.M. Alopecia areata: clinical presentation, diagnosis, and unusual cases. *Dermatol. Ther.*, 2011; 24: 348–354. doi: 10.1111/j.1529-8019.2011.01413.x. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
3. Govinda Das Sen. Bhaishajya Ratnavali. In: Virechana Prakarana – Ichchhabhedhi Rasa Yoga. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2021; 91.
4. Govinda Das Sen. Bhaishajya Ratnavali. In: Kushta Chikitsa Prakarana – Gandhaka Rasayana Yoga. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2021; 842.
5. Śārṅgadhara. Śārṅgadhara Saṁhitā. In: Madhyama Khanda, Adhyaya 7 – Triphala Guggulu Yoga. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2021; 202.
6. <https://shop.sdpayurveda.com/product/nagavalli-ointment/>
7. Śārṅgadhara. Śārṅgadhara Saṁhitā. In: Madhyama Khanda, Adhyaya 9 – Taila Kalpana (Bhringaraja Taila Yoga). Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2021; 215.
8. Chakrapanidatta, commentator Charaka samhita, Chikitsa sthana, Adhyaya 26/132-133, 3rd ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krushnadas Academy, 2020; 606.
9. Sushruta. Sushruta samhita samhita with the nibandhasangraha commentary of sri dalhanaacharya nidanasthana adhyaya 13/3n2023 edition, choukhamba surbharatin prakashan, Varanasi, 2023; 318.
10. Govinda Das Sen. Bhaishajya Ratnavali. In: Kushta Chikitsa Prakarana – Indralupta Chikitsa. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2021; 839.
11. <https://www.1mg.com/otc/capro-hairich-ayurvedic-capsule-otc694247>